

large and positive though the ΔH terms also make some contribution. The reported values of ΔH and ΔS indicate the involvement of two phenolic oxygen atom in coordination¹¹. The values of $\log K_1$ for the Cu(II)¹², Ni(II)¹³ and Zn(II)¹⁴ complexes of catechol are 14.10, 8.36 and 12.26 respectively which are nearer to the values for the PV complexes of these metals. This also supports the coordination of PV through two phenolic groups.

The colour and λ_{\max} of the PV is pH dependent. Below pH=7.0 it gives a maxima at 590 nm. At pH 7.5 two maxima at 443 and 590 nm and at pH \approx 8.0, only one maxima at 500 nm was observed. In the pH range 9.5-10.0, there is no maxima, however, a flat maxima at 460 nm is observed. The mixture containing metal and dye in the ratio of 1 : 1 gave the maxima at 609 nm in the pH range 8.5-9.0 for Mn(II), 580 nm in the pH range 8.2-8.7 for Fe(II), 600 nm in the pH range 7.5-8.3 for Co(II), 590 nm in the pH range 7.0-7.65 for Ni(II), 598 nm in the pH range 5.5-6.5 for Cu(II) and at 598 nm in the pH range 6.7-7.3 for Zn(II). The absorbance of the complexes remain almost constant in the pH ranges given for their formation and the values of $\bar{n}=1$ in these pH ranges indicate the complete formation of 1 : 1 complex. This combining ratio was further confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation.

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Solid Reflectance Spectral Studies on Some Uranium(V) Compounds

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SSELBIN and coworkers have reported UCl_5 complexes with ligands containing N, P, As, Bi, O, S, Se and Te as donor atoms.¹ Paul and coworkers have also characterised UCl_5 complexes with nitrogen and oxygen donors^{2,3}. Solid reflectance spectra reported^{2,3} were recorded in a limited range because of the sensitivity of the complexes to moisture and lack of adequate arrangements to record spectra in an inert atmosphere. Therefore it could not be proved conclusively that there was no disproportionation of U(V) into U(IV) and U(VI). In fact disproportionation occurred to a significant extent during all the spectral measurements. The only peak corresponding to the $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_6$ transition (840-870 nm) was recorded. The absorption bands due to $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8$, $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_7'$ and $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8'$ transitions had not been studied due to the non-availability of spectrophotometer with the required range at that time. In the present investigations UCl_5 complexes have been prepared in the dry box under dry nitrogen from UCl_5 solution in $SOCl_2$ and base solution in $SOCl_2$ as reported^{2,3}. Solid reflectance spectra of the complexes (600-2100 nm) were recorded using Beckman DK-2A Spectrophotometer (Fig. 1). The complexes were

Fig. 1. (A) $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ pyridine, (B) $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ quinoline, (C) $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ isoquinoline, (D) $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ benzil, (E) $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ anthrone.

well powdered, sealed by silicone high vacuum grease between the requisite plates in the dry box in dry nitrogen for recording their spectra.

Results and Discussion

A few publications⁴⁻⁷ which contain electronic spectral information on U(V) species deal with this species in an octahedral or nearly octahedral environment. Four low energy transitions are predicted. These transitions can be denoted as $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8$, $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_7'$, $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8'$ and $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_6$. But experimentally not only four bands rather four groups of bands are generally observed^{4,6,7}.

In the complexes $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ pyridine, $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ quinoline, $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ isoquinoline, $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ benzil and $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ anthrone, the $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8$ transition produces a weak band between 1650-1660 nm. The $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_7'$ transition produces a group of strong bands between 1435-1470 nm. The $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8'$ transition exhibits two bands of roughly equal intensity at ~ 950 nm and ~ 1000 nm. The $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_6$ transition occurs between 850-870 nm in these complexes. Strong peaks between 600-700 nm and between 1050-1150 nm which are characteristic of U(IV) species^{8,9} were absent in UCl_5 complexes with nitrogen donors indicating that there is no disproportionation of U(V) into U(IV) and U(VI). However, in $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ benzil and $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ anthrone complexes a very strong band at ~ 1010 and ~ 1095 nm respectively indicates appreciable disproportionation of U(V) into U(IV) and U(VI) in complexes with oxygen donors.

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Relation Between the Lattice Energy and Melting Point of Alkali Hydroxides

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THE concept of lattice energy of similar class of compounds is an important consideration while dealing with different phenomena of chemical interest. For example, in a set of closely related substances it is invariably used to explain their solubility behaviour, relative thermal stability and the melting and boiling processes associated with them. Thus in latter instance, a direct proportionality between lattice energy (U_0) and absolute melting point (T_m) viz., $U_0/T_m \approx \text{const.}$, has been fairly established for a number of related systems including s, d and f block metals^{1,2}, molecular solids³⁻⁵ and ionic compounds^{6,7}. A similar correlation amongst the lattice energy and corresponding absolute boiling point (T_b) is also described elsewhere⁶⁻⁷.

The lattice energies of alkali hydroxides reported by different workers⁸⁻¹² appear to vary quite considerably. It was, therefore, thought desirable to examine the correspondence of existing lattice energy and melting point of these compounds for a ready approval of the former. In this attempt the relevant data^{8-12,13} along with observed U_0/T_m ratio are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RELATION BETWEEN U_0 AND T_m OF ALKALI HYDROXIDES*

Alkali Hydroxide	ref. 8	ref. 9	ref. 10	ref. 11	ref. 12	T_m (°K)
LiOH	215(0.30)	230(0.32)	229(0.32)	205(0.28)	205(0.28)	723
NaOH	205(0.35)	209(0.35)	196(0.33)	166(0.28)	176(0.30)	592
KOH	181(0.29)	184(0.29)	173(0.27)	145(0.23)	153(0.24)	634
RbOH	172(0.30)	174(0.30)	166(0.29)	137(0.24)	147(0.26)	573
CsOH	158(0.29)	165(0.30)	157(0.29)	130(0.24)	136(0.25)	546
Mean U_0/T_m	0.31	0.31	0.30	0.25	0.27	

* Values preceding parentheses are U_0 in K cal mole⁻¹ while those within parentheses refer to the observed ratio of U_0/T_m .

Table 1 reveals that the proportionality ratio between U_0 ⁸⁻¹⁰ and T_m ¹² is fairly constant. The associated ratio for different alkali hydroxides is very close to 0.30. According to other sources of U_0 ^{11,12}, the U_0/T_m , however, give lower average values of 0.25 and 0.27 respectively. Thus, a much better correspondence between U_0 and T_m in the former as compared to latter appears to support the genuinity of U_0 data according to sources⁸⁻¹⁰, quite convincingly.

One would, likewise, expect a constancy of the ratio of U_0/T_b in the present system. In view of